

DELIVERABLE

2.1.2 – DESCRIPTION OF THE CONSIDERED VALIDATED INDICATORS AMONG THE IDENTIFIED ONES AND ASSOCIATED METHODOLOGY, STATE OF CONSCIOUSNESS AFTER WATERBATH STUNNING OF BROILERS AND TURKEYS

Contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Methodology used	4
3. State of consciousness after waterbath stunning of broilers and turkeys.....	6
4. References	24

1. Introduction

This document is part of the **sub-activity 2.1** “*Relevant animal welfare indicators*” and concerns to the priority area related to the state of consciousness after waterbath stunning of broilers and turkeys.

In this welfare issue, animal (ABI), resource (RBI) and management-based indicators (MBI) and its methods of assessment for each legal requirement are identified and described. The description of the methods is based on scientific publications or Competent Authorities’ official inspection documents provided to the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA. There might be some methods not described in this document, the list is not exhaustive. The experts from the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA chose the most relevant ones according to their knowledge and the available scientific data.

Afterwards, the indicators and methods of assessment are evaluated according to their validity, feasibility and reliability (see definition below) in order to deliver to Competent Authorities (CA) useful information for official controls. However, some indicators are not developed in this document because their methodology will be part of the deliverable 2.2.2 output namely to propose better methods of animal welfare assessment for the legislative requirements most difficult to implement. Thus, they will be developed in future working programs.

Definitions

Legal requirement: a requisite of the EU legislation to be assessed during the official controls.

Example: Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 3, Paragraph 1: “*Animals shall be spared any avoidable pain, distress or suffering during their killing and related operations*”

Indicator: an occurrence, observation, record or measurement which has a proven relationship with the legal requirement, which can be:

- **Animal-based indicator (ABI):** a response of an animal or an effect on an animal used to assess its welfare. It can be taken directly on the animal or indirectly and includes the use of animal records.
Example: Wing flapping as ABI of consciousness.
- **Resource-based indicator (RBI):** an evaluation of a feature of the environment in which the animal is kept or to which it is exposed.
Example: Frequency, minimum average current (mA/bird) and duration of exposure to the waterbath.
- **Management-based indicator (MBI):** an evaluation of what the animal unit manager or stockperson does, and which management processes or tools are used.
Example: Presence of standard operating procedures.

Method for the assessment (= method): a form of evaluation of the indicators that might be used in the frame of the verification of the legal requirements.

Example: Check the stunner is delivering the minimum electrical parameters to each bird in the waterbath. For this, knowing the species of the birds and the frequency of the current used, determinate in Council Regulation 1099/2009 to minimum amount of current (mA) that should go through every bird. Take the average amount of current delivered during your period of control (A) and divide it by the maximum number of birds that can be immersed in the waterbath at the same time and compare the two values.

Validity: The extent to which an indicator is meaningful in terms of providing information on a legal requirement concerning an animal or a group of animals.

Reliability: The extent to which results are largely the same when the same observer repeats assessments after receiving reasonable training or the agreement between two or more observers after they have received reasonable training.

Feasibility: Capacity to be applicable to different waterbath stunning equipment and at least have the potential to be applied in the field (slaughterhouse).

2. Methodology used

In this document, for each legal requirement ABI, RBI or MBI are identified and their method of assessment described and evaluated according to the validity, reliability and feasibility. This information is summarized in tables where their validity, reliability and feasibility are scored according to information found in the scientific literature, the ranking of the CAs and the expert knowledge. The ranking exercise of the CAs was carried out during the first meeting between the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA and the CAs of Member States (available in deliverable D.1.1.3, annexes, 5, 6, and 7). We chose a rating method with three levels, as follow in table 1 below.

Table 1: Rating method used for the assessment of the validity, reliability and feasibility of the indicators

	Gap of knowledge	X (low)	XX (moderate)	XXX (high)
Validity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No data found in literature No data on ranking exercise from CAs No expert opinion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Literature shows low correlation between the legal requirement and the indicator/method <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average score from 0 to 2 (on a scale of 5) in CAs ranking exercise <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expert opinion with experience of poor level of validity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Literature shows moderate correlation between the legal requirement and the indicator/method <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average score higher than 2 and lower than 4 (on a scale of 5) in CAs ranking exercise <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expert opinion with experience of moderate level of validity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Literature shows high correlation (with causality link) between the legal requirement and the indicator/method. <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average score higher than 4 (on a scale of 5) in CAs ranking exercise <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expert opinion with experience of high level of validity
Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No data found in literature No data on ranking exercise from CA No expert opinion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Literature shows low reliability <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average score from 0 to 2 (on a scale of 5) in CAs ranking exercise <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expert opinion with experience of poor level of reliability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Literature shows moderate reliability <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average score higher than 2 and lower than 4 (on a scale of 5) in CAs ranking exercise <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expert opinion with experience of moderate level of reliability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Literature shows high reliability <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average score higher than 4 (on a scale of 5) in CAs ranking exercise <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expert opinion with experience of high level of reliability
Feasibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No data found in literature No data on ranking exercise from CA No expert opinion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Material needed:</i> High cost/low availability material (e.g. gas meter, dust meter) <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Time to performed:</i> More than 60 min <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Ease to access:</i> Difficult access or not possible in more than one type of structure <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Animal manipulation:</i> Biological sampling (e.g. blood, swab) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Material needed:</i> moderate cost of the material (e.g. thermometer, hygrometer) <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Time to be performed:</i> 30-60 min <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Ease of access:</i> Not easy to access (e.g. to upper tiers) or not easy to apply in all farm/slaughterhouses <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Animal manipulation:</i> Some animal manipulation with no biological sampling (e.g. check foot pad) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Material needed:</i> no or low-cost material (e.g. tape measurer) <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Time to be performed:</i> less than 30 min <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Ease of access:</i> Easy to access and feasible in all kind of structure <p><i>And/or</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Animal manipulation:</i> No animal manipulation

3. State of consciousness after waterbath stunning of broilers and turkeys

The bird's welfare assessment at the slaughterhouse includes all processes from the arrival of birds until their death. This can be grouped in three main phases: 1) pre-stunning (*i.e.*, unloading from the truck, lairage, handling and removing of birds from crates or containers and shackling); 2) stunning and 3) bleeding. The indicators and the methods addressed below focus on bird's welfare assessment associated to the waterbath stunning and bleeding phases in broilers and turkeys.

All ABIs described in this document should be performed by the operators, the animal welfare officer (AWO) and the official veterinarian (OV). While operators should assess the ABIs in all birds, the AWO should assess that the operators are assessing them correctly in a representative sample of birds. OV can check that both business operator (BO) and AWO are assessing the ABIs and the procedure correctly in a representative sample of birds. Sample size of animals to be checked for second level control (by AWO or OV) can be calculated using the Excel tool developed by EFSA (2013b). Briefly, it takes into consideration the test sensitivity (sensitivity of indicator or combination of indicators), the slaughtered population, the maximum allowed threshold failure rate (% of confidence) and the required accuracy. Thus, the AWO and the OV should evaluate a sample of birds any time there is a change in the slaughtering (*e.g.*, specie, size of the animals, etc).

3.1. Legal requirement: *"Animals shall be spared any avoidable pain, distress or suffering during their killing and related operations"* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 3, Paragraph 1)

During waterbath stunning broilers and turkeys might experience pain, distress or suffering associated with:

- a) Pre-stun shocks at the entrance of the waterbath
- b) Delayed induction of unconsciousness
- c) Failure in onset of unconsciousness
- d) Recovery of consciousness before death

a) Pre-stun shocks at the entrance of the waterbath

Pre-stun shocks occur when a part of a bird gets in contact with the electrified water before the head is immersed, causing severe pain before onset of unconsciousness. Moreover, pre-stun shocks may cause withdrawal reactions of wings or head that could lead to lack of head contact with the electrified water. This will lead to failure in stunning and the bird might arrive conscious to the section of carotids and bleeding (EFSA, 2019). Birds flapping their wings due to pre-stun shock can hit at the same time the neighbouring shackled birds causing an under-controlled cyclical situation of wing flapping and pre-stun shocks as such the wings may be more likely to contact the electrified water. No birds must receive pre-stun shocks. If any, corrective and preventive measures should be applied. Pre-stun shocks are usually associated with an inadequate waterbath design. If this situation occurs, the corrective measure is no other than redesign of the shackle line (EFSA, 2019).

3.1.1. ABIs:

- Vigorous wing flapping: prolonged bout of continuous, rapid wing-flapping.
- Withdrawal reactions of wings or head: fast avoiding movement of the neck, head or wing.
- Vocalisations: single or repeated short and loud shrieking (screaming) at high frequencies.

- *Description of the method:* The ABIs associated with pre-stun shocks are assessed in birds entering the waterbath. Birds are suffering from pre-stun shocks if suddenly exhibit one or more of the previous ABIs at the entrance of the waterbath (vigorous wing flapping, withdrawal reactions of wings or the head, or vocalisation).
- *Evaluation of the method:* The validity of the indicators is high, but the feasibility of the method depends on the design of the waterbath equipment and the degree of accessibility of the inspector to observe the shackled birds at the entrance of the waterbath stunner, so depending on the slaughter field condition it can range from low to high. For this reason, as it cannot be feasible in all slaughter field condition, the feasibility is scored as low. The assessment of pre-stun shocks should be prioritised using ABIs but when it is not possible due to poor slaughterhouse design, the inspector should rely on RBIs and the related method described below. So far, the reliability of these ABIs has not been assessed.

ABI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Vigorous wing flapping	xxx	x	Gap of knowledge
Withdrawal reactions of wings or head	xxx	x	Gap of knowledge
Vocalisations	xxx	x	Gap of knowledge

3.1.2. RBIs:

- Design, construction and maintenance of the shackle line (EFSA, 2019)
- Design, construction and maintenance of the ramp (EFSA, 2019)
 - *Description of the method:* The shackle line and the ramp should be designed and built to avoid wing flapping at the entrance of the waterbath and ensure that the first part of contact with the waterbath is the head, if not, pre-stun shock may occur. In order to assess pre-stun shocks using RBIs first, check the shackle size is appropriate for the specie of bird and size as shackles have the potential to cause pain and damage to birds by compressing the tissues of the shank. In this sense, shackles must have multiple slots of varying tapering gauges in order to limiting leg compression (HSA, 2015). Second, check if the live bird shackling area includes bird-calming measures (*e.g.*, dim blue light, breast comforters). Third, check if the shackle line has curves, inclinations, drops or bunched transitions near to the entrance to the waterbath that may cause irregular movements and provoke wing flapping. The ramp of the waterbath should be steeply inclined smooth ascending over the entrance to the waterbath. Furthermore, the ramp should be electrically isolated by insulating material and can be checked in the manufacturer's information. If not, check the entry ramp is covered with a material that acts as an insulator. Moreover, visually check there is no flow of water coming from the waterbath running down the ramp (HSA, 2015).
 - *Evaluation of the method:* The feasibility and reliability of this indicators are high. However, the validity will depend on the correlation with ABIs.

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Design, construction and maintenance of the ramp and the shackle line	Gap of knowledge	xxx	xxx

3.1.3. MBIs:

- Records of frequency of maintenance of the equipment
- Presence of certificate of competence and staff training.
- Presence or absence of standard operating procedures (SOP) on the monitoring of pre-stun shocks.
 - *Description of the methods:* Check the records of frequency of maintenance of the waterbath stunning equipment. Moreover, check if the shackles and the earthing bars are wet and routinely cleaned with detergent for bird's plumage and carbonised debris removal. Check the presence of certificate of competence and staff training and SOP on the monitoring of pre-stun shocks and the.
 - *Evaluation of the methods:* These methods are highly feasible and reliable but low valid as the records of frequency of maintenance, the presence of SOP and certificate of competence does not ensure neither the operators put in practice what it is written in the SOP nor they are fully skilled and trained to monitor the stun effectiveness. Additionally, validity also depends on the quality of the records. Thus, the validity of all indicators is low as it does not ensure birds are not experiencing avoidable pain, distress or suffering from waterbath stunning to their killing.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Records of frequency of maintenance	x	xxx	xxx
Certificate of competence	x	xxx	xxx
Presence of SOP	x	xxx	xxx

b) Delayed induction of unconsciousness

If the loss of consciousness is not immediate after the immersion into the waterbath, birds will experience pain, distress and suffering until the loss of consciousness occurs, due to poor electrical contact. If it occurs, corrective and preventive measures should be applied.

3.1.4. ABIs:

- Time interval between head immersion and tonic seizure: tonic seizure can be assessed when bird arch and stiff the neck and wings held tightly close to the body.
- Presence of wing flapping while the head is immersed in the waterbath and before tonic seizure occurs.
 - *Description of the method:* Assess the time in seconds between head immersion and tonic seizure occurs. Correct stun should immediately induce tonic seizure after head immersion (< 1s). During this time, assess if the birds show wing flapping, indicator of scape attempt while consciousness. To evaluate this, record from a sample of

birds how many flaps their wings while immersed in the waterbath before tonic seizure occurs.

- *Evaluation of the method:* The validity of the indicators is high, but the feasibility related to this method is low as it depends on how accessible is the waterbath stunner to check if the birds show signs of delay of consciousness. Moreover, it also depends on the line speed (the faster is the line speed, the lower is the feasibility). So far, the reliability of these ABIs has not been assessed yet.

ABI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Time interval between head immersion and tonic seizure	xx	x	Gap of knowledge
Wing flapping before tonic seizure	xxx	x	Gap of knowledge

3.1.5. RBIs:

- Frequency, minimum average current (mA/bird) and duration of exposure to the waterbath stunning according to the regulation (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex I, Chapter II, Point 6.3)
 - *Description of the method:* Check the stunner is delivering the minimum electrical parameters to each bird in the waterbath. For this, knowing the species of the birds and the frequency of the current used, determinate in Council Regulation 1099/2009 to minimum amount of current (mA) that should go through every bird. Take the average amount of current delivered during your period of control (A) and divide it by the maximum number of birds that can be immersed in the waterbath at the same time and compare the two values.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* The validity of this indicator is low as all birds in a multiple birds waterbath may not receive the same current because of differences in individual variability in electrical resistance and, for some of them, it might be not sufficient to induce unconsciousness. Furthermore, it requires a regular calibration and maintenance of the equipment according to the manufacturer's instructions (HSA, 2015). Otherwise, the electrical parameters intended to use can differ from those applied and the current be lower than expected and fail to induce a state of unconsciousness. The feasibility is high but there is a gap of knowledge on its reliability.

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Frequency, minimum average current (mA/bird) and duration of exposure to the waterbath	x	xxx	Gap of knowledge

3.1.6. MBIs:

Associated with delayed loss of consciousness after immersion of the head:

- Records of frequency of calibration and maintenance of the equipment. It should be according to the manufacturer specifications.
- Presence of certificate of competence and staff training.
- Standard operating procedures (SOP) of the monitoring of stun effectiveness.
 - *Description of these methods:* check the records of frequency of maintenance and calibration of the waterbath stunning equipment. Moreover, check if the shackles and the earthing bars are wet and routinely cleaned with detergent for bird's plumage and carbonised debris removal. Check the certificate of competence and staff training and the presence of SOP on the monitoring of stun effectiveness.
 - *Evaluation of these methods:* these indicators are highly feasible and reliable but low valid. The presence of SOP and certificate of competence does not ensure neither the operators put in practice what it is written in the SOP nor they are fully skilled and trained to monitor the stun effectiveness. Hence, it does not ensure birds are not experiencing avoidable pain, distress or suffering from waterbath stunning to their killing.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Records of frequency of calibration and maintenance of the equipment	x	xxx	xxx
Presence of SOP	x	xxx	xxx
Certificate of competence	x	xxx	xxx

c) Failure in onset of unconsciousness

Poor electrical contact, too short exposure times, inappropriate electrical parameters or the inability of the equipment to deliver minimum current to all the birds with cause failure in onset of unconsciousness leading to pain and fear (EFSA, 2019).

3.1.7. ABIs:

- Tonic seizure: Rigid backward bending of the neck and tucked wings, sometimes accompanied by small and quick muscular contractions
- Breathing: Respiratory cycle of inspiration and expiration.
- Spontaneous blinking: the bird opens/closes eyelid on its own (fast or slow) without stimulation.
- Corneal or palpebral reflex: Reflex action of the eye resulting in automatic closing of the eyelid when the cornea is stimulated.
- Vocalisation: Single or repeated short and loud shrieking (screaming) at high frequencies.
 - *Description of the method:* The incidence of bird's consciousness is recorded from a representative sample of birds between the exit of the waterbath until neck cutting. It is recommended to assess the state of consciousness by using a minimum of two ABIs per stage and checked simultaneously on each animal (EFSA, 2013a).

Although there are several ABIs to assess the state of consciousness, the most relevant are tonic seizures, breathing and spontaneous blinking and as additional ABIs, corneal or palpebral reflex and vocalisations.

For these relevant ABIs, the outcomes of a failure in onset of unconsciousness are:

- 1) Absence of tonic seizures recognized by the absence of an arched and stiff neck (*i.e.*, necks appear parallel to the ground) and wings held tightly close to the body.
 - 2) Presence of breathing, recognized by either beak or cloaca movements associated to sustained/presence of breathing, including laboured breathing.
 - 3) Presence of spontaneous blinking when observing the bird's eyes.
 - 4) Presence of corneal or palpebral reflex by holding the bird's head and touching the eye with a feather or a finger and the bird show response to this stimulus.
 - 5) Presence of vocalisations.
- *Evaluation of the method:* The different ABIs for the assessment of failure in the onset of unconsciousness differ on the degree of validity, feasibility and reliability. The feasibility will depend on the logistics of the slaughterhouse (*e.g.*, accessibility to the slaughter line, line speed, space between shackled birds, position of the observer, etc). In this sense, tonic seizure is easy to assess only if there is good visibility inside the waterbath. Sometimes, once the bird exceeds the waterbath, the tonic seizure might have disappeared. Breathing is highly valid as when it is observed, it indicates that the bird is conscious, but it is considered medium in feasibility as birds presented in dorsal and not ventral to the observer, the assessment of the beak or cloaca movements is impaired. Vocalisations although easy to assess, their validity are not considered to be high as birds that do not show these behaviours could be considered unconscious but in fact, they could be conscious. On the contrary, ABIs like corneal or palpebral reflex are more valid but less feasible as requires holding the head of the animal and touch the eye being time-consuming and only feasible at slaughterhouses with low-throughput rates. The validity of these ABIs are based according to the perceived sensitivity (*i.e.*, percentage of truly conscious birds considered conscious) from experts in this field (EFSA, 2013a). Sensitivity was 78% for tonic seizures, 89% for breathing, 94% spontaneous blinking, 93-94% for corneal or palpebral reflex, and 52% for vocalisations. Scores on reliability and feasibility of all indicators were retrieved from Competent Authorities' opinion. As there is a lack of knowledge on the reliability of these indicators scientifically, further research on checking intra- and inter-observer repeatability is needed and the reliability of some of these ABIs will be addressed in deliverable 3.2.4. (*i.e.*, tonic seizures, breathing, spontaneous blinking and vocalisations).

ABI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Tonic seizures	xx	xx	xx
Breathing	xxx	xx	xx
Spontaneous blinking	xx	x	xx
Corneal or palpebral reflex	xx	x	xx
Vocalisation	xx	xxx	xx

3.1.8. RBIs:

- Frequency, minimum average current per animal and duration of the immersion of the bird's head into the water at stunning as stated in Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex I, Chapter II, Point 6.3.
 - *Description of the method:* Check the electronic device of the waterbath stunning and see if the electrical parameters are in the range stipulated in Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009. Moreover, it is fundamental to check the records related to frequency of calibration of the measuring device. On the other hand, in order to assess the duration of the immersion of the bird's head, hang an object that serves you as reference in the shackle line and time how long it lasts to cross the waterbath. It should last a minimum of 4 s to ensure birds do not evade stunning by keeping their head up.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Although this method is highly feasible and reliable, the validity is low because each bird in a multiple birds waterbath may not receive the same current because of differences in electrical resistance among birds and, for some of them, it might be not sufficient to induce unconsciousness. Furthermore, it requires a regular calibration and maintenance of the equipment according to the manufacturer's instructions (HSA, 2015).

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Electrical parameters and duration of the immersion	x	xxx	xxx

3.1.9. MBIs:

- Presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness or sensibility of birds between the exit from the waterbath stunner and neck cutting.
- Presence of staff assessing the state of consciousness of birds between the exit from the waterbath stunner and neck cutting.
- Frequency of staff shifts.
 - *Description of the methods:* Check the presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness and the personnel performing the assessment. Check if there is a staff rotation to avoid boredom and fatigue at regular intervals.
 - *Evaluation of the methods:* Neither the presence of SOP, the observation that personnel assess the consciousness of birds nor the frequency of staff shifts ensure the personnel assess properly the state of consciousness nor re-stun conscious birds. Thus, although these indicators are highly feasible and reliable, the validity is low.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence of SOP	X	XXX	XXX
Personnel assessment of consciousness and sensibility of birds	X	XXX	XXX
Frequency of staff shifts	X	XXX	XXX

d) Recovery of consciousness before death

This section is also linked to Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 4, Paragraph 1 (section 3.3.2. of the present document) where “*The loss of consciousness and sensibility shall be maintained until the death of the animal*”.

3.1.10. ABIs:

- Wing flapping.
- Breathing: Respiratory cycle of inspiration and expiration.
- Corneal or palpebral reflex: reflex action of the eye resulting in automatic closing of the eyelid when the cornea is stimulated.
- Spontaneous swallowing (deglutition reflex).
- Head shaking: Rapid shaking of the head, most times accompanied by stretching and/or withdrawal movements of the head.

- *Description of the method:* The incidence of recovery of bird’s consciousness before death must be recorded before and after bleeding until the entrance to the scalding tank in order to check the bird is dead before dressing. This is due to the fact that some birds although stunned, may recover consciousness. It is recommended to assess the state of consciousness by using a minimum of two ABIs and checked simultaneously on each animal (EFSA, 2013a).

Although there are several ABIs to assess the recovery of consciousness, the most relevant are wing flapping and breathing and, as additional indicators, corneal or palpebral reflex, spontaneous swallowing and head shacking (EFSA, 2013a). For these ABIs, the outcomes of recovery of consciousness are:

- 1) Presence of wing flapping.
- 2) Presence of breathing: recognized by the presence of either beak or cloaca movements, including laboured breathing.
- 3) Presence of corneal or palpebral reflex by holding the bird’s head and touching the eye with a feather or a finger and the bird show response to this stimulus.
- 4) Spontaneous swallowing (deglutition reflex).
- 5) Presence of head shacking.

- *Evaluation of the method:* The different ABIs for the assessment of the state of consciousness differ on the degree of, validity, feasibility and reliability. Thus, the ABIs must be chosen by their strengths and limitations but also considering the logistics of the slaughterhouse (e.g., accessibility to the slaughter line, line speed, space between shackled birds, position of the observer, etc). In this sense, wing

flapping although easy to assess, its validity is not considered to be high as birds that do not show these behaviours could be considered unconscious but in fact, they could be recovering consciousness. On the contrary, ABIs like corneal or palpebral reflex are more valid but less feasible as requires holding the head of the animal and touch the eye being time-consuming and only feasible at slaughterhouses with low-throughput rates. The validity of spontaneous swallowing and head shaking are medium as birds that do not show these behaviours do not mean necessarily that are unconscious.

The validity ranked for these ABIs according to their sensitivity when the outcomes observed using ABIs where compared with the results obtained using electroencephalography (EEG) under experimental conditions was 76% for wing flapping, 89% for breathing, 93-94% for corneal or palpebral reflex (EFSA, 2013a). No literature was found on sensitivity of spontaneous swallowing and head shaking. Scores on reliability and feasibility of all indicators were retrieved from Competent Authorities' opinion. As there is a gap of knowledge on the reliability of these indicators scientifically, further research on checking intra- and inter-observer repeatability is needed and the reliability of some of these ABIs will be addressed in deliverable 3.2.4 (*i.e.*, wing flapping, breathing, spontaneous swallowing and head shaking).

ABI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Wing flapping	XX	XXX	XXX
Breathing	XXX	XXX	XXX
Corneal or palpebral reflex	XXX	XX	XX
Spontaneous swallowing	XX	XX	XX
Head shaking	XX	XX	XX

3.1.11. RBIs: There is no specific RBI for this requirement.

3.1.12. MBIs:

- Presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness or sensibility in birds between the end of the stunning process and death.
- Check that persons responsible for stunning or other nominated staff correctly assess the consciousness and sensibility of birds between the end of the stunning process and death as it is planned in the SOP in a representative and sufficient sample of birds.
- Frequency of staff shifts.
 - *Description of the methods:* Check the presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness and the personnel do as it is planned in the SOP in a representative sample of birds. Check if there is a staff rotation to avoid boredom and fatigue at regular intervals.
 - *Evaluation of the methods:* The presence of SOP, the observation that personnel assess the consciousness of birds nor the frequency of staff shifts ensure the personnel assess properly the state of recovering consciousness. Thus, although the method is highly feasible and reliable, the validity of the indicators ranges is low as

it depends if the personnel is paying attention to all birds and are skilled to assess properly that a bird is recovering consciousness.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence of SOP	x	xxx	xxx
Personnel assessment of bird's recovery of consciousness and sensibility	x	xxx	xxx
Frequency of staff shifts	x	xxx	xxx

3.2. Legal requirement: “The loss of consciousness and sensibility shall be maintained until the death of the animal” (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 4, Paragraph 1)

3.2.1. ABIs:

In this section the ABIs, description of the method an evaluation of the method are the same as described in section 3.3.1.4. Recovery of consciousness before death.

3.2.1. RBIs:

In this section the RBIs, description of the method an evaluation of the method are the same as described in section 3.3.1.4. Recovery of consciousness before death.

3.2.3. MBIs:

- Presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness or sensibility in birds between the end of the stunning process and death.
- Check that persons responsible for stunning or other nominated staff correctly assess the consciousness and sensibility of birds between the end of the stunning process and death as it is planned in the SOP in a representative and sufficient sample of birds.
- Frequency of staff shifts.
 - *Description of the methods:* Check the presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness and the personnel do as it is planned in the SOP in a representative sample of birds. Check if there is a staff rotation to avoid boredom and fatigue at regular intervals.
 - *Evaluation of the methods:* The presence of SOP, the observation that personnel assess the consciousness of birds nor the frequency of staff shifts ensure the personnel assess properly the state of consciousness nor re-stun conscious birds. Thus, although these indicators are highly feasible and reliable, the validity is low as it depends on what the personnel do in case of birds recover consciousness (re-stunning).

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence of SOP	x	xxx	xxx
Personnel assessment of consciousness and sensibility of birds	x	xxx	xxx
Frequency of staff shifts	x	xxx	xxx

3.3. Legal requirement: “The waterbath shall be designed in such a way that the level of immersion of the birds can be easily adapted” (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.6.)

3.3.1. ABIs: Bird’s level of submersion into the waterbath.

- *Description of the method:* check if the shackled animals of the same batch have similar size. Then, visually inspect that all bird’s head in the batch are fully submerged including the eyes and the cranium and up to the base of the wings (HAS, 2015).
- *Evaluation of the method:* this method is highly feasible and reliable, but the validity is low as it depends on how accessible is the waterbath to visually check the level of submersion of bird’s head of different batches that vary in average size.

ABI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Bird’s level of submersion into the waterbath	x	xxx	xxx

3.3.2. RBIs:

- Adequate waterbath height and water level.
 - *Description of the method:* check if the waterbath allow vertical adjustment by the personnel to quickly raise or lower the waterbath whilst it is filled with water. In addition, check if the depth of the water is appropriate which means that when the waterbath is raised it ensures complete submersion of the heads for the entire length of the waterbath (HSA, 2015).
 - *Evaluation of the method:* validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Adequate waterbath height and level	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.3.3. MBI:

- SOP about the abattoir personnel checking and adjusting if necessary, the height of the waterbath and the water level.
 - *Description of the method:* Check the presence of the SOP about the abattoir personnel checking and adjusting if necessary, the height of the waterbath and the water level.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* The validity is low because the presence of SOP does not ensure the operators adjust the waterbath height and level when needed. On the other hand, the feasibility and reliability are high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence of SOP	x	xxx	xxx

3.4. Legal requirement. *“The electrodes in waterbath stunning equipment shall extend the full length of the waterbath. The waterbath shall be designed and maintained in such a way that when the shackles pass over the water they are in continuous contact with the earthed rubbing bar”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.7.)

3.4.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.4.2. RBIs: Visual inspection

- Length of the electrode placed in the water with an extension of the full length of the waterbath.
- Continuous contact with the earthed rubbing bar.
 - *Description of the method:* Visually check the waterbath when its empty if the length of the electrodes covers the full length of the waterbath. If it is not possible, check the technical documentation of the waterbath manufacturer. Additionally, visually check the earthed rubbing bar is firm and in constant contact with each metal shackle in which a bird is restrained, for the whole duration that each bird’s head is submerged in the waterbath. Likewise, make sure occupied shackles do not overlap onto neighbouring shackles, because this may reduce or alter the flow of current through a bird. Thus, it may impair an effective stun and causing pre-stun shocks to the birds (HSA, 2015).
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Length of the electrode placed in the waterbath and shackles in contact with the earthed rubbing bar	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.4.3. MBIs: There is no specific MBI for this requirement.

3.5. Legal requirement. *“The whole length of the shackle line up to the point of entry into the scald tank shall be easily accessible in case animals have to be removed from the slaughter line”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.3.)

3.5.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.5.2. RBIs:

- Assessment if the design, construction and maintenance of the shackle line allows easy access to the birds at any point
 - *Description of the method:* check if the design, construction and maintenance of the slaughter plant allow that personnel have access to birds quickly and safely in emergencies at any point on a shackle line, from shackling to entry to a scald tank.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

Indicator	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Accessibility to the whole length of the shackle line	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.5.3. MBIs: There is no specific MBI for this requirement.

3.6. Legal requirement. *“Access to the waterbath stunning equipment shall be available to allow the bleeding of birds that have been stunned and remain in the waterbath as a result of a breakdown or delay in the line”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.9.)

3.6.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.6.2. RBIs:

- Design, construction and maintenance of the waterbath stunning allowing access to the bird
 - *Description of the method:* Check if the design, construction and maintenance of the slaughter plant allow that personnel can easily have access to birds that are in the waterbath stunning equipment in case there is a result of a breakdown or delay in the line (e.g., opening the panel of protection in order to have quick access to waterbath area).
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Accessibility to the waterbath stunning equipment	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.6.3. MBIs: There is no specific MBI for this requirement.

3.7. Legal requirement. *“Waterbath stunning equipment shall be fitted with a device which displays and records the details of the electrical key parameters used. These records shall be kept for at least one year.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.10.)

3.7.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.7.2. RBIs: There is no specific RBI for this requirement.

3.7.3. MBIs:

- Presence of a device that displays and records the details of the electrical key parameters used and it is regularly calibrated.
- Records of frequency of calibration and maintenance of the equipment.
 - *Description of the methods:* The check should concern the existence of a systematic recording of electrical key parameters during all production periods. The records during the last one-year period should be provided by the FBO. The frequency and the report of calibration of the maintenance of the equipment shall be requested.
 - *Evaluation of the methods:* the validity, feasibility and reliability of both indicators are high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence of a device that displays and records the details of the electrical parameters	xxx	xxx	xxx
Records of frequency of calibration and maintenance	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.8. Legal requirement. *“Business operators shall ensure that persons responsible for stunning or other nominated staff carry out regular checks to ensure that the animals do not present any signs of consciousness or sensibility in the period between the end of the stunning process and death.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 5, Paragraph 1)

3.8.1. ABIs: In this section the ABIs, description of the method and an evaluation of the method are the same as described in section 3.3.1.3. Failure in onset of unconsciousness and 3.3.1.4. Recovery of consciousness before death.

3.8.2. RBIs:

- Presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness or sensibility in birds between the end of the stunning process and death.

3.8.3. MBIs:

- Check that persons responsible for stunning or other nominated staff correctly assess the consciousness and sensibility of birds as described in the SOP regularly in a representative sample of birds.
 - *Description of the method:* Check that persons responsible for stunning or other nominated staff correctly assess the consciousness and sensibility of birds between the end of the stunning process and death as it is planned in the SOP in a representative sample of birds.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* This method is highly feasible and reliable, but the validity is low as it might depend on how well-trained and skilled is the personnel at assessing signs of consciousness.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Regular checks on signs of consciousness	x	xxx	xxx

3.9. Legal requirement. *“Those checks shall be carried out on a sufficiently representative sample of animals and their frequency shall be established taking into account the outcome of previous checks and any factors which may affect the efficiency of the stunning process.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 5, Paragraph 2)

3.9.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.9.2. RBIs:

- The business operators assess the consciousness and sensibility with the appropriate frequency on a sufficiently representative sample of birds.

- *Description of the method: Check the business operators are assessing the state of consciousness and sensibility every time is a change in the slaughtering (e.g., specie, size of the animals, etc).*
- *Evaluation of the method: Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.*

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Personnel assessment of consciousness with the appropriate frequency on a sufficient sample of animals	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.9.3. MBIs: There is no specific MBI for this requirement.

3.10. Legal requirement. *“When the outcome of the checks indicates that an animal is not properly stunned, the person in charge of stunning shall immediately take the appropriate measures as specified in the standard operating procedures drawn up in accordance with Article 6(2)” (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 5, Paragraph 3.)*

3.10.1. ABIs:

- Consciousness and sensibility before and after re-stunning of birds using at least two ABIs described in 3.3.2.1. and related to Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, 4, Paragraph 1.
 - *Description of the method: check if personnel properly assess bird’s state of consciousness as described in 3.3.2.1. of the present manuscript.*
 - *Evaluation of the method: Same evaluation as described in section 3.3.2.1. of the present manuscript.*

3.10.2. RBIs:

- Presence or absence of back-up stunning methods in sufficient number.
 - *Description of the method: Check the presence or absence of back-up stunning methods. Should be an adequate number of them and placed close enough to different points of the shackle line to re-stun the birds quickly if they are ineffectively stunned or show signs that are recovering consciousness.*
 - *Evaluation of the method: The validity is low as the presence of back-up stunning methods does not ensure the personnel re-stun conscious birds. On the other hand, this indicator is highly feasible and reliable.*

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence or absence of back-up stunning methods	x	xxx	xxx

3.10.3. MBIs:

- Presence or absence of SOP.

- Record of re-stunned birds.
 - *Description of the method:* Check that personnel correctly assess the consciousness and sensibility of birds between the end of the stunning process and death and take appropriate measures as it is planned in the SOP as well as the records of re-stunned birds.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* The validity is low because the presence of SOP does not ensure neither the operators are fully skilled and trained to monitor the stun effectiveness nor they put re-stun birds when show signs of consciousness. The records may not be reflecting that all the birds that showed signs of consciousness were re-stunned. On the other hand, the feasibility and reliability is high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence or absence of SOP	x	xxx	xxx
Record of re-stunned birds	x	xxx	xxx

3.11. Legal requirement. *“Business operators shall ensure that (...) slaughter operations (...) are only carried out by persons holding a certificate of competence for such operations (...), demonstrating their ability to carry them out in accordance with the rules laid down in this Regulation.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 7)

3.11.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.11.2. RBIs: There is no specific RBI for this requirement.

3.11.3. MBIs:

- Staff with certificate of competence delivered by the corresponding EU member state.
 - *Description of the method:* Check that all staff involved in slaughter operations have certificate of competence by the corresponding EU member state.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Certificate of competence	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.12. Legal requirement. *“(...) The checks (...) shall include (...) indicators designed to detect signs of unconsciousness and consciousness or sensibility in the animals; indicators designed to detect the absence of signs of life in the animals slaughtered (...) in accordance with Article 4(4); criteria for determining whether the results shown by the indicators referred to in point (b) are satisfactory; the circumstances and/or the time when the monitoring must take place; the number of animals in each sample to be checked during the monitoring; appropriate procedures to ensure that in the event that the criteria referred to in point (c) are not met, the*

stunning or killing operations are reviewed in order to identify the causes of any shortcomings and the necessary changes to be made to those operations.”
(Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 2.)

3.12.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.12.2. RBIs: There is no specific RBI for this requirement.

3.12.3. MBIs:

- Presence or absence of SOP that includes a control procedure of stunning.
 - *Description of the method:* Check if there is a presence of SOP that includes a control procedure of stunning. Check non-conformities and that remedial actions are well listed and relevant.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* The validity is low because the presence of SOP does not ensure neither the operators are fully skilled nor trained. On the other hand, the feasibility and reliability is high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence of SOP	x	xxx	xxx

3.13. Legal requirement. “Business operators shall put in place a specific monitoring procedure for each slaughter line.” (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 3)

3.13.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.13.2. RBI: There is no specific RBI for this requirement.

3.13.3. MBIs:

- Presence or absence of SOP for every slaughter line.
- Check non-conformities and that remedial actions are well listed and relevant for every slaughter line.
 - *Description of the method:* Check if there is a presence of SOP that indicate setting and using characteristics of slaughter equipment, a procedure to assess animal's death to guarantee animals are dead before further dressing or scalding. Check non-conformities and that remedial actions are well listed and relevant for every slaughter line.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence of SOP	xxx	xxx	xxx
Non-conformities and remedial actions	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.14. Legal requirement. *“The frequency of the checks shall take into account the main risk factors, such as changes regarding the types or the size of animals slaughtered, or personnel working patterns and shall be established so as to ensure results with a high level of confidence.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 4)

3.14.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.14.2. RBIs: There is no specific RBI for this requirement.

3.14.3. MBIs:

- Frequency and distribution of the checks.
 - *Description of the method:* The check shall be redone for each type of production if change occur in stunning system and if new operators are acting.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Frequency and distribution of the checks	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.15. Legal requirement. *“For the purpose of paragraphs 1 to 4 of this Article 16, business operators may use monitoring procedures as described in the guides to good practice referred to in Article 13. Community guidelines concerning monitoring procedures in slaughterhouses may be adopted in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 25(2).”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 5 and 6)

3.15.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.15.2. RBIs:

- Presence or absence of monitoring procedures as described in the guides to good practice.
 - *Description of the method:* Check the presence of guides to good practice and the monitoring procedures described on it. Then, check if business operators use them.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

RBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence of monitoring procedures	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.15.3. MBIs:

- Reports related to the monitoring procedures.
 - *Description of the method:* Check the reports and the content related to the monitoring procedures.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Reports related to the monitoring procedures	xxx	xxx	xxx

3.16. Legal requirement. “Member States shall encourage the development and dissemination of guides to good practice to facilitate the implementation of this Regulation.” (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 13, Paragraph 1)

3.16.1. ABIs: There is no specific ABI for this requirement.

3.16.2. RBIs: There is no specific RBI for this requirement.

3.16.3. MBIs:

- Presence or absence of guides to good practice.
- Dissemination of the information related to guides to good practice.
 - *Description of the method:* Check if there are guides to good practice and if its information is disseminated.
 - *Evaluation of the method:* Validity, feasibility and reliability of this indicator is high.

MBI	Validity	Feasibility	Reliability
Presence or absence of guides to good practice.	xxx	xxx	xxx
Dissemination of the information related to guides to good practice.	xxx	xxx	xxx

4. References

- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). 2012. Scientific Opinion on the electrical requirements for waterbath stunning equipment applicable for poultry. *EFSA Journal* 10(6):2757.
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